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Print ISSN: [3006-2497](#) Online ISSN: [3006-2500](#)Platform & Workflow by: [Open Journal Systems](#)**Impact of Schools Heads Passive Communication Style on Teachers' Emotional Stress at Secondary Level in District Bannu****Rifat Ullah**

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asifalihan124@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

Success in the school is often attributed to the communication styles of the school's heads', specifically to how they manage the emotional state of the teachers. However, there is still a lack of information on how the communication styles of school head's affect the emotional stress of their teachers. The purpose of this study was to investigate the schools heads' communication styles and its impact on teachers' emotional stress at secondary level in Bannu District. The study was descriptive in nature so descriptive survey design was used by the researcher to conduct the study. All 130 (Male/Female) secondary schools and all 1627(Male/Female) secondary schools' teachers working of Bannu district was the population of the study. Stratified sampling technique was used to draw sample for the study. The sample size was justified using Krejice & Morgan (1970) formula. The sample of the study was comprised of 56 secondary schools and 327 secondary school male and female teachers working in secondary schools in Bannu District. Two questionnaires for the teachers were used to collect data from the sampled respondents. The collected data was analyzed by using Mean, Standard deviation. Independent samples Mann-Whitney U test were used to find out required findings and conclusions. Eventually recommendations were made by the researcher. It was found that passive communication style was up to the mark in all phase, while head ignored situation which needs solution on urgent basis. Similarly mean scores of emotional stress items in the scale fall as the average showing that teachers' emotional stress was not up to the mark in all phase. Government may ensure school heads' to practice best methods of interacting with their teachers in order to reduce stress levels among teachers. The government may conduct seminars, meetings and workshops where

teachers should be provided teaching roles and given the opportunity to evaluate the merits of various targeted communication styles for them.

Keywords: Heads Passive Communication Styles, Teachers Emotional Stress, Secondary Level Bannu

INTRODUCTION

Webster's (2021) dictionary defines "communication" as "the process by which information is conveyed from one person to another using established conventions of speech, writing, or other graphic or physical means."

The basis of success in today's digital workplace is effective internal communications (IC). It's just as crucial how a message is conveyed as what's being conveyed. The values, beliefs, and customs of an organization are its "culture," and in today's competitive business environment, that culture may be a decisive competitive advantage. But if the organization is unable to successfully transmit these aspects of its culture, it will lose this competitive edge. First, there has to be a robust system of internal communications that follows best principles if workers are going to comprehend and act in accordance with the company's broad aims and values. Just as important as the content of your communication is how it is conveyed. (SpriggHR, 2020).

The manner in which an individual expresses themselves to others is known as his or her communication style or communication pattern. De Vries, et al. (2009) describe communication styles as the distinctive ways in which individuals employ verbal, paraverbal, and nonverbal clues to transmit their identities, connections, and messages to others in the course of social interactions. One way to characterize a person's communication style is by looking at how they handle negotiations. (Reece, Brandt, & Howie, 2010).

Statement of the Problem

The research problem is "Impact of Schools Heads' Communication Styles on Teachers' Emotional Stress at Secondary Level in Bannu District" was to provide that how much the communication styles of the schools heads' effect on teachers' emotional stress. It is believed that positive emotional responses from teachers are a direct result of strong educational leadership. Teachers' and heads' working relationships are crucial to a school's success. Teachers are likely to feel negatively about the school as a whole if school heads have poor communication skills. Depression, worry, and a general inability to get anything done are all direct results. School heads' communication styles have a direct impact on teachers' levels of work satisfaction in Pakistan. The school heads' has a significant impact on the emotional stress experienced by the teachers. Teachers' work satisfaction and emotional well-being are impacted by the leadership team's ability to effectively communicate with their teachers. The emotional stress of teachers is increasingly attributable to the communication styles of school heads'. It's possible that the position of school heads will vary from institution to institution due to the fact that heads have varying approaches to communicating. Their styles and personalities can have a significant impact on the emotional stress of the teachers. This area of research is of great importance in the field of education but little attention was paid to it in Pakistan. This study for the first time investigated impact of school heads' communication styles on teachers' emotional stress at

secondary school level in Bannu district Khyber Pakhtunkhwa which differentiate this study from the earlier studies on the subject and fills the gap.

Objectives of the study

The following were the objectives of the study

1. To evaluate passive communication style of the school heads' at secondary level in Bannu District.
2. To assess the level of emotional stress of teachers at secondary level.
3. To compare emotional stress of male and female teachers in secondary schools.
4. To compare school heads' passive communication style by gender.
5. To investigate the impact of school heads' passive communication style on teachers' emotional stress.

Research Questions of the study

1. What communication styles are used by school heads' at secondary level?
2. What is the level of emotional stress of teachers at secondary level?

Null Hypothesis:

The following were the Null Hypothesis of the study:

1. **H₀ 1:** There is no statistical difference between male and female teachers regarding their passive communication style of their heads.
2. **H₀ 2:** There is no statistical difference between male and female teachers regarding their emotional stress.
3. **H₀ 3:** There is no statistical impact of school heads' passive communication style on teachers' emotional stress at secondary level.

Significance of the Study

The emotional well-being of teachers was seen to be directly tied to how well school heads' convey their vision to the teachers. While school heads are widely recognized as key players in enhancing educational settings, little was known about the ways in which their interactions with educators shape educators' feelings, relationships with administration, and productivity on the job. Teachers' stress and negative emotions may have had a severe impact on their classroom performance, as well as their work satisfaction and eventual burnout. This study was defensible on the following grounds:

1. The present study would contribute useful information which communication styles of the school heads' effect on teachers' emotional stress.
2. The findings of the study would be helpful in providing guidelines to the schools heads' to improve their communication styles with the teachers such as talking, listening, good relationship and behavior.

1.7 Delimitations of the study

The study was delimited to passive communication style. It was delimited to Public Secondary Schools of District Bannu. All Secondary schools' male and female teachers working in Secondary Schools of district Bannu came under the purview of the study.

REVIEW OF RELATED KITERATURE

This part deals with review of available literature related to the study. The chief purpose of the study was; Impact of Schools Heads' Communication Styles on Teachers' Emotional Stress at Secondary Level" is reviewed here.

Communication

Communication is essential to human survival. One of the main goals of human communication is the development of shared understanding, as discussed by Ibrahim (2016).

Richmond, McCroskey, and Powel (2012) write, "Humans' ability to gain knowledge and experience relies on the sharing of information in the form of concepts, views, beliefs, and emotions."

Communication is essential in any setting, but it is especially crucial in educational institutions where rules and regulations must be followed. Given the broad reaching changes in education today, educational institutions require competent school heads' who are strong communicators. Effective leaders, according to Lunenburg and Irby (2006), spend most of their time talking to teachers in the school.

Since the communication styles of school heads' is correlated with teachers' emotional stress and satisfaction, Blase (1986) concludes that heads' communication style has an impact on teachers' performance.

The Latin term *commuicare*, meaning "to share," is where our modern word "communication" gets its start. Because of communication, many people are privy to the same data. It includes a wide variety of elements, including ideas, theories, curiosities, pursuits, and texts. Information transfer from one location to another is one definition. To be published by John Wiley in 2021.

"Paul Copley says in 2008 that "communication appears to be the answer to the unpleasant separation between self and other, private and public, innermost thought and outer world." Depending on the context, the word "communication" may either include a wide range of actions or be narrowly defined (for example, by saying that one must have a "conscious intent" to persuade). He further says that it is because communication is both a ubiquitous occurrence and a distinct academic field that its definition is so elusive.

The sender, the channel, and the receiver are the three most fundamental components of every successful communication. Because he has complete knowledge of the subject, the sender is the most confused person in the conversation. However, the recipient lacks complete background information about the sender and the subject matter of the information being sent.

Passive Communication Style

Passive communication, as defined by Sherman, R. (2015), occurs when a person puts the needs of others before their own. People who are poor communicators tend to bottle up their feelings so they can get along with others and avoid arguments. In situations when the speaker fears rejection for voicing their issues, they may resort to this mode of communication. People who are mostly passive in their communication tend to have poor self-esteem and difficulty understanding their own needs. They have a habit of putting their faith in other people but not in themselves.

Many personality traits are linked to this kind of interaction. Avoiding conflict, having trouble accepting responsibility or making choices, conforming to others' tastes, declining praises, heaving audible sighs, asking for permission when it's not necessary, shifting blame, and so on are all examples of such behaviours. Passive communication is shown in a lot of nonverbal actions. People who communicate passively tend to lower their voices, talk slowly, and otherwise shrink themselves. They also try to avoid making eye contact and jiggle a lot.

People that are passive in their communication styles may provoke a wide range of responses from listeners. Common emotions they experience include worry, sadness, anger, helplessness, and perplexity. They worry that nothing they do will make a difference, and they get depressed when they feel helpless about their situation. Resentment builds up in passive communicators when they believe their needs aren't being satisfied, and confusion sets up when they can't put a name to their emotions. When someone communicates passively, the receiver is often left feeling disappointed, guilty, and skeptical that the sender understands what they want. People who are inactive in conversations sometimes feel worried before they begin and then wounded or furious afterward.

People who have trouble speaking up for themselves are more likely to foster dependent relationships, lack confidence in themselves, and promote others excessively. Rather of immediately addressing the source of their pain, those who engage in passive communication wait until the issue has worsened before responding. The person feels bad and confused after this outburst, and so they revert to their passive communication styles.

There are, nevertheless, many situations when passive forms of communication are required. When the topic at hand is relatively trivial, when the difficulties precipitated by the disagreement are more severe than the conflict itself, and when emotions are running high are all times when this approach may be appropriate.

Passive Communication Examples

Passive communication may be shown in a variety of ways, as described by Sherman, R. (2015).

Some people who have trouble speaking out may say something like, "I hope somebody remembers to take out the garbage." rather than directly asking a family member to do so. Many family members are likely to miss such subtle hints, leaving the passive communicator frustrated and the family member who failed to catch on perplexed.

Some individuals just allow other people's opinions and sentiments prevail over their own. If you and your colleagues have planned a lunch at a restaurant that doesn't offer many vegetarian alternatives, you may not want to rock the boat by bringing it up for fear of coming off as tough or fussy.

It's possible for passive communicators to use a tone of apology or softness in their speech. A person may preface an opinion or remark with an apology or a qualification. To illustrate, a passive speaker may respond to a topic at a meeting with, "Maybe this is a silly way to put it, but have you thought about the issue this way." Because of insecurity and the fear of being labeled as judgmental or rude, this occurs.

Communicators that are too passive tend to:

1. Not standing up for oneself
2. Permit other parties to knowingly or unknowingly violate their rights
3. Keep their emotions, wants, and preferences bottled up.
4. Have a habit of using a softer, more contrite tone of voice than necessary
5. Make awkward body language and avoid making eye contact.

Signs of Passive Communication Style

We've all participated in passive communication at some time in our lives. Here are some examples:

1. We firstly put off getting to the point. We use oblique language and subtle clues in the hopes that the recipient will get the point.
2. Second, we are very quiet and humble in our delivery. We aren't sure of ourselves and worry that others will judge us harshly or dismiss our ideas and efforts.
3. Third, we have passive body language, which includes slouching and a lack of eye contact. Insecurity and lack of confidence may be shown by poor posture and hesitating motions.

Impacts of Passive Communication

Consequences of such a passive-voice approach to communication include:

1. Anxiety because life appears out of control
2. Depression because they feel trapped and hopeless
3. Resentment (unknown) because demands are unmet
4. Confusion because they neglect their own feelings
5. Are stunted in their development due to the avoidance of tough topics.
6. May have their wants and preferences ignored.
7. When you keep quiet about things that bother you, you end up supporting decisions that are bad for everyone.
8. The in-considering of others may leave you feeling angry, resentful, or stressed out.
9. You may suppress your emotions in the sake of maintaining harmony. However, you are feeling helpless and forlorn.

The Process of Emotion

Emotions have three components: internal experiences, external physiological reactions, and external behavioural responses, as stated by the American Psychological Association (2019).

Subjective Experiences

In order to experience an emotion, one needs first have a personal encounter, or a stimulus. While it's true that sentiments may be expressed regardless of one's background, the events that give birth to those feelings are typically quite individual.

The modest impression of a hue to the overwhelming emotional effect of loss or the pleasure of a wedding is all examples of subjective experiences. An individual's spectrum of emotional responses to any particular situation is very distinctive and contextual, spanning from mild to extreme. One person may experience intense sadness after the death of a loved one, while another may be consumed with anger and guilt.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This part consists of procedure and pattern of the study. The researcher does effort to explain related procedure and method for the documentation of this study

Research Design

A research design is the plan or proposed to conduct a research. According to Creswell and Creswell (2017), quantitative research is the investigation into human or social problems. To status that quantitative research aims to determine the relationship between an independent and dependent variable in a population by gathering data and numerically analyzing this relationship. The study was descriptive in nature. Therefore, the researcher was used survey method design for analysis.

Population

The population of the study was comprised of all Government Boys’ and Girls High Schools’ teachers (N=1637; ASCR 2020-21) working in public secondary schools in District Bannu of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Table 1 Number of Teachers as a Population

District	Boys	Girls	Total
Bannu	1068	569	1637

(EMIS, 2020, 21)

Sampling and Sample Size

Sampling is the process of selecting a subset of a population to serve as a stand-in for the whole. The sample is a subset of the population that accurately represents the whole. Lance & Hattori, (2016). Using an online sample calculator (<http://www.surveysystem.com>), a sample size of N=1637 was determined to achieve a 0.05 level of significance with 95 percent confidence. After that, a simple random sample method (found at <https://stattrek.com/survey-research/basic-random-sampling.aspx>) was used to choose the participants. The researcher utilized a stratified random sampling method since it would have been unreasonable to choose an equal number of male and female teachers.

Table 2 Number of Teachers as a Sample

Respondents	Male	Female	Total
Sample	220	107	327

Curry, L.A., ET AL (2013) explain the sample size Rule of Thumb as below

The population Size	The Sample Dimension
101 to 1,000	10%
1,001 to 5,000	5%
5,001 to	3%
10,000+	1%

Cuury et al (2013) stated that there is no clear cut answer for the correct sample size; it depends upon the study and the nature of the population under investigation

Research Instrument

Self-developed two questionnaires were used to collect data from the respondents. The questionnaires were (communication style questionnaire and emotional stress questionnaire). The questionnaires were comprised forty four statements at all in which communication style questionnaire had Eleven statements and emotional stress questionnaire bear thirty three statements. Five point Likert scale was used for both o the questionnaires. The response category was varied from “Never to Always.” The Scoring for the both instruments were used as; Never 1, Seldom 2, Occasionally 3, Frequently 4, Always 5. All teachers were asked to put a tick mark on of the most appropriate response of their choice.

Validity and Reliability

For the validation of the both of the questionnaires, the researcher requested a panel of experts to refine the items, in order to make the questionnaires simple and understandable. The experts and professors analyzed and reviewed the questionnaires by ensuring the content validity. In the light of feedback received from the experts, the questionnaires were finalized and total 38 statements were approved in both o the questionnaires. For determining the reliability of this instrument, 30 respondents were selected. Cronbach’s Alpha was applied to calculate internal consistency of items. The alpha value was found higher ensuring taking further step of data collection.

Method of Data collection

In general, the researcher got permission from school principals and the district education officer. To guarantee conformity with ethical norms, the researcher obtained prior and informed consent. Keeping in mind the local traditions, the researcher collected data directly from male respondents and indirectly from female respondents. The procedure of compilation of information was appropriately organized and respondents took the responsibility and filled the questionnaires which were returned on time.

Data Analysis Techniques

The collected data were put in “SPSS-23” used for treatment. To find out the answer for objective number one, i-e school heads’ communication styles and two and i-e teachers emotional stress mean, standard deviation, as well as To compare male and female school heads’ communication styles independent sample Mann-Whitney U- test was used.. To assess the impact’ linear regression was also used.

ANALYSIS AND INTREPRETATION OF DATA

This portion deals with the collection and analysis of the data. The primary data were obtained through opinionative, which was fielded to the respondents in district Bannu. The data were analyzed with the help of tables for discussion and interpretation.

Research Question 1: What communication styles are used by school heads’ at secondary level?
Table 3 shows School Heads’ Passive Communication Style item wise Mean and Standard Deviation

S.No	Statement	N	Mean	Std
1.	The head expresses his/her feelings to others.	327	2.34	.753
2.	The head does not express his/her feelings because of the fear that this may cause unlikeness from others.	327	2.27	1.221
3.	The head says that he/she does not care for other opinions	327	2.66	.585
4.	The head keeps silence on many matters to avoid uncertainty in school.	327	2.85	.599
5.	The head shows carefulness in selection of words while communicating with subordinates.	327	3.05	1.134
6.	The head avoids giving bold stance on important issues of the school.	327	2.68	.691
7.	The head keeps poor eye contact with others in meetings.	327	2.80	.992
8.	The head avoids conflicting situation in school.	327	2.65	.753
9.	The head ignores situation which needs solution on urgent basis.	327	2.18	.970

Mean score of Passive Communication Style items is 2.8294

Classification of Mean:

1. 0 to 2.49 is below Average
2. 2.50 to 3.49 is Average
3. 3.50 to 5.00 is above Average

Table 3 illustrates mean scores of passive communication style items in the scale fall in the average mean category 2.50 to 3.49, showing that passive communication style of school heads are not up to the mark in all phase.

Research Question 2: What is the level of emotional stress of teachers at secondary level?

Table 4 Showing Teachers’ Emotional Stress at Secondary level

S.#	Statement	N	M	SD
1.	I feel stress when too many work demands are being made on me	327	2.36	0.580
2.	I feel stress when I take extra classes.	327	2.78	0.758
3.	I feel stress when I teach in noisy conditions.	327	2.86	0.976
4.	I feel stress in meetings with school head when he does not properly listen to me.	327	2.72	0.702
5.	I become stress when the school head negatively criticizes my work.	327	2.80	0.762

6. The head inappropriate attitude stresses me.	327	2.11	0.787
7. I feel stress when I teach to overcrowded classes.	327	2.36	0.579
8. I feel stress when there is a lack of coordination between me and the school head.	327	2.64	0.706
9. Poor working conditions in school stress me.	327	2.84	0.788
10. Poor communication skills of head stress me.	327	2.62	0.769
11. I feel stress when the head does not give importance to my opinions in the school matter	327	2.54	0.686
12. I feel stress when head does not acknowledge my services.	327	2.42	0.850
13. I become stressed when the head uses harsh language in staff meeting.	327	2.32	0.695
14. I feel stress when head does not openly speak about any matter.	327	2.79	0.848
15. The heads' unpleasant facial expression stresses me.	327	2.88	0.917
16. I feel stress when the head gives me a short deadline about some work.	327	2.53	0.710
17. I become emotionally stress when the head undermines my job performance.	327	2.58	0.668
18. I feel stress when the head frequently reminds me my previous mistakes.	327	2.33	0.601
19. Inadequate physical facilities in school make me stress.	327	2.26	0.892
20. I become stress when the head taunts me on small issues.	327	2.31	0.968
21. Students' misbehavior in class makes me stress.	327	2.84	0.766
22. Poor working relationship with head make me stress.	327	2.13	0.786
23. Lack of professional development opportunities make me stress.	327	2.88	0.775
24. I feel stress when the head does not include me in decision making.	327	2.31	0.743
25. Incompetent clerical staff behavior makes me stress.	327	2.95	0.947
26. I feel stress when the head does not communicate us the exam schedule on time.	327	2.16	0.992
27. I feel stress when I teach in unsuitable thermal conditions.	327	2.95	0.911
28. The head poor eye contact stresses me.	327	2.82	0.710
29. I feel stress when the head does not communicate classes' timetable on time.	327	2.89	0.889

Mean score of all items is 2.82

Classification of Mean:

1. 0 to 2.49 is below Average
2. 2.50 to 3.49 is Average
3. 3.50 to 5.00 is above Average

Table 4 illustrates mean scores of emotional stress items in the scale fall in the average mean category 2.50 to 3.49, showing that teachers’ emotional stress not up to the mark in all phase.

H₀ 1: There is no statistical difference between male and female teachers regarding their passive communication style of their heads.

Table No. 5 Shows comparison between male and female regarding Passive Communication Style

Category	Respondents	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mann-Whitney U test	P-value
1	Male	219	25.48	2.74	11522.500	.753
2	Female	107	25.43	2.77		

Table 5 shows sample sizes, standard deviation, U-test and p-value for male and female groups. After checking the normality we can applied non parametric test alternative to t test which is Mann Whitney u test. The mean of male is 25.48 and female mean is 25.43, standard deviation for male is 2.74 and female is 2.77. The U-test is 11522.500 and the p-value is .753. Since the p-value is greater than 0.5 it indicates that null hypothesis is accepted. It shows that there is no significance difference between both groups regarding passive communication styles.

H₀ 2: There is no statistical difference between male and female teachers regarding their emotional stress.

Table No. 6: Shows comparison between male and female regarding Teachers’ Emotional Stress

Category	Respondents	No	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mann-Whitney U test	P-value
1	Male	220	78.89	7.099	11488.00	.723
2	Female	107	78.34	6.803		

The above table shows sample sizes, standard deviation, U-test and p-value for both male and female groups. After checking the normality we can apply non parametric test alternative to t test which is Mann Whitney u test. The mean of male is 78.89 and female mean is 78.34, standard deviation for male is 7.099 and female is 6.803. The U-test is 11488.00 and the p-value is .723. Since p-value is greater than 0.5 it indicates that null hypothesis is accepted. It indicates that there is no difference between both male and female in emotional stress. Emotional stress of both genders is same.

Table 5: Comparison of Male and Female School Heads Communication Styles on Teacher’s Emotional Stress

Tests of Normality

Category	Kolmogorov- Smirnov			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	Df	Sig.	Statistic	Df	Sig.
TESPS	0.267	624	0.000	0.783	624	0.00

In the above TESPS represents teachers’ emotional stress and passive style.

Table 6 School Heads Communication Styles on Teacher’s Emotional Stress

Category	Mann-Whitney U test	P-value
Teachers’ Emotional Stress & Passive Style	3899.00	0.00

In the above table we can check teachers’ emotional stress with communication styles. After checking the normality we can apply non parametric test alternative to t test which is Mann-Whitney u test. We can see from the entire table that the p-value is less than (0.05). It showed that there is statistically significance and there is an effect of school heads ‘communication styles on teachers’ emotional stress.

Null Hypotheses (H₀) There is no significant impact of passive communication style on teachers’ emotional stress at secondary level.

Table 7 (a): Regression Coefficients Summary

Predictor Variable	Unstandardized Coefficient	SE	β	T	p-value
Constant	1.267	0.143	—	8.860	0.000
PCS	0.384	0.072	0.312	5.333	0.000

Predictor: Passive Communication Style

The un-standardized coefficients further indicate that for every one-unit increase in passive communication style, emotional stress increases by 0.384 units, The overall model significance (p = 0.000), the regression model is statistically valid and reliable. These results lead to the rejection of the null hypothesis, confirming that the communication styles of school heads have a measurable and significant impact on teachers' emotional well-being. It implies that leadership communication plays a crucial role in shaping the school climate and staff morale, and improvements in communication approaches may reduce stress among teachers.

Table 7 (b): Model Summary

R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F-value	Sig. (p)
0.611	0.373	0.369	96.234	0.000

The model yielded an R² value of 0.373, indicating that approximately 37.3% of the variance in teachers’ emotional stress can be explained by the influence of passive communication styles. The predictor was statistically significant at p < 0.05, with passive communication style (β = 0.312, t = 5.333, p = 0.000). This suggests that as the intensity of communication style increases, so does

the level of stress experienced by teachers.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This portion deals with the results, discussion, conclusions, and recommendations of the study.

Results

It was found that passive communication style was up to the mark in all phase, while head ignored situation which needs solution on urgent basis. Similarly mean scores of emotional stress items in the scale fall as the average showing that teachers' emotional stress was not up to the mark in all phase.

Discussion

The finding of this study showed that adopting communication styles by school heads' had a great impact on teachers' emotional stress. They conveyed their information to their staff. It has a greater impact than any other factor. Misunderstandings and arguments are inevitable outcomes of a lack of effective communication. Snodgrass and Blunt (2009) stress the need of clear, direct, and precise communication. Most school heads aren't naturally gifted communicators, but with effort, they may develop and hone their abilities (Juliana, 2016).

Conclusions

In the light of the present study it was concluded that school heads' communication style has a great impact on teachers' emotional stress at secondary level. The present learning was guided by the following conclusions:

It was concluded that passive communication style of heads was typical as perceived by teachers. It was also concluded that the communication styles of school heads' and teachers' emotional stress of both the genders were up to the mark in all aspects however teachers emotional stress was not satisfactory.

Recommendations

The following suggestions were drawn from the findings and conclusions of this study.

- Government may ensure school heads' to practice best methods of interacting with their teachers in order to reduce stress levels among teachers.
- The government may conduct seminars, meetings and workshops where teachers should be provided teaching roles and given the opportunity to evaluate the merits of various targeted communication styles for them.

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